

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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D6.5 Data Management Plan

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Authors	Blanco-Velázquez FJ, Alonso Martín F, Bravo-García J, González-Peñaloza F and Anaya-Romero M
Contributors	ALL

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been reviewed by the NOVASOIL consortium according to the national reports and comments received

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	14/04/2023	EVENOR	Draft version circulated by email
2	V1.1	24/04/2023	ALL partners	Comments and inputs received
3	V2.0	25/04/2023	EVENOR	Second version circulated by email
4	V3.0	16/09/2024	EVENOR	Inputs based on comments received
5	V4.0	30/10/2025	EVENOR	Inputs based on datasets generated

Data Management Plan (DMP) versions

The DMP is a document which evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life-cycle of all research datasets of the NOVASOIL project. The table below shows all the planned versions of NOVASOIL DMP, this final version shows the data produced and the data management policy adopted at the end of the project.

Version	Expected by project month (M)
D6.2	6
D6.4	18
D6.5	36

Project Consortium

Nº	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

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1 Data Management Plan (DMP)

The DMP is a document that provides details regarding all the data collected and generated within a project. The way of research data are handled, organised, licensed and made openly available to the stakeholders, and how they will be preserved and stored beyond the project. As well as, the DMP provides motivations when versions or some parts of the project research data cannot be openly shared on account of third-party copyright issues, confidentiality or personal data protection requirements, or when open dissemination could compromise the project achievements. The details and the final number of the project datasets could vary along the project so the DMP must be constantly updated.

2 Executive summary

The general objective of the NOVASOIL project is to highlight the benefits for society and the environment from the investment in soil health. The main expected outcome of the project is a toolbox for the analysis of the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health. This toolbox will be based on a set of good examples from Europe and other countries and the needs and demands of the society. The toolbox will include a categorisation of the models and business cases taking into account: a) sustainable soil management under different land uses and climatic conditions; b) products based on practices promoting soil health; c) consumption and certification practices conducive: d) the reuse of land and e) sustainable soil management in the context of the EU Taxonomy Regulation.

The NOVASOIL multi-actor and multidisciplinary team brings together 16 partners in 10 countries, covering representative typologies of actors involved in soil health and business models (farmer organisation, research institutions, consultancy companies, etc).

NOVASOIL uses qualitative and quantitative analytical methods, such as surveys, key actors, stakeholders' workshops, case studies and modelling.

The project will generate and collect several different types of research data: numerical and textual data as well modelling data. Research teams will convert data from repository formats and will make them available in well-known and documented open formats to allow accessibility, reusability and long-term preservation (see Table 1 for details)

Type of data	Format used during data processing	Formats for sharing re-use and preservation
Numerical or textual tabular data	Microsoft Excel or similar (.xls/ .xlsx/ .ODF)	Comma-separated values (.csv) Microsoft Excel or similar (.xls/ .xlsx/ .ODF) as an exception when format conversion to

		.csv is not feasible because of the presence of special characters.
Qualitative textual data	Microsoft word or similar (.doc/ .docx/ .odt)	Rich Text Format (.rtf) or text (.txt)
Simulation model data		The mathematical model is saved using standard differential equations symbols in .csv and .txt. Simulated values are saved as numerical data, as specified above.
Statistical data	STATA format (.dta), R format (.Rdata)	Comma-separated values (.csv), R format (.Rdata)

As well as, documentation files explaining all relevant details regarding data collection, processing methodologies and quality assurance will be deposited in institutional or public repositories along with the datasets in .odt, .rtf or .pdf formats.

The project potentially re-uses a variety of existing data from different sources. For example, data from CAP Strategic Plans (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans_en), Statistical Yearbook World Food and Agriculture from FAO (<https://www.fao.org/3/cc2211en/online/cc2211en.html>), data from descriptions and reports created by Local Authorities, etc.

The data will be deposited in repositories in compressed folders.

All the data generated may be of interest to different potential users as researchers, students, policy makers, stakeholders, farmers, practitioners working on soil health business design, etc.

The data could also be used as a source for topic-related studies, comparisons and for different analyses.

3 FAIR Data

The current DMP follows the EU guidelines (<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>) and describes the data management procedures according to the FAIR principles. Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement and subject to Regulation 2018/1725.

The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/679).

The acronym FAIR identifies the main features that the project research data must have in order to be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, allowing thus for maximum knowledge circulation and return of investment.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Following previous initiatives and experience from the consortium, at the moment of the publication of project results, each research team deposits and describes the relative underlying dataset(s) in institutional or public data repositories. In order to identify the deposited items, the repositories can attribute persistent unique identifiers such as DOI (Digital Object Identifiers). Partners are strongly recommended to use the persistent unique identifiers to cite the datasets as underlying data within their research publications.

The chosen data repositories (see Table 2 and 3 for the list of the chosen data repositories) support standard descriptive metadata to ensure datasets indexing and discoverability. They comply with the OpenAIRE 3.0 requirements for data archives. As a consequence, the project datasets will be visible through the OpenAIRE portal, facilitating project reporting procedures.

All relevant documentation explaining data collection procedures and analysis will be made available along with the data, in order to guarantee intelligibility, reproducibility and the validation of the project findings. All datasets will be described using standard metadata and according to the OpenAIRE guidelines in order to ensure also metadata interoperability for datasets indexing and discoverability.

NOVASOIL research data will be organised in datasets, which will be named collections of data units with the same focus and scope. This DMP has identified the following common rules for dataset labelling in order to promote data visibility, discoverability, citation and permanent online tracking.

The **recommended title** for each dataset consists of:

NOVASOIL_<WP number>_<Task number>_<Task title>_<additional information specifying coverage of data>_<date and version number (if revisions or updates are required)>

The version number of the datasets will be added at the end of the title in case of data revisions to help identifying the dataset updates especially in repositories that do not track versioning automatically.

The DMP suggests the following rules for file labelling:

- For dataset file(s):

NOVASOIL_WPnumber_Tnumber_coverage_date(YYYY.MM.DD)_vn.fileextension

- For the dataset relevant documentation explaining data collection procedures and analysis (such as manuals, methodologies, etc):

NOVASOIL_WPnumber_Tnumber_coverage_date(YYYY.MM.DD)_vn_READM
E.fileextention

WPnumber= Work Package number

Tnumber= Task number

Vn= version number

3.2 Making data openly accessible

NOVASOIL aims to make research data openly available, whenever possible, to allow dissemination, validation and re-use of research results. For these, all files will be converted to standard and well-documented open formats and the datasets will be deposited together with all the additional and relevant documentation and explanation.

However, restrictions on data access or the impossibility to share them have been considered only in the following cases:

- When collected data belong to a third party which denies permission for sharing them on account of confidentiality and proprietary issues;
- Protection of personal data of key informants involved in surveys, focus groups, interviews, stakeholders' workshops and case studies.

Consequently, all possible and legitimate actions and strategies may be adopted to allow data sharing including:

- Obtaining copyright permissions from third-party data owners to be allowed to re-use, reproduce and distribute the collected data;
- Converting files to standard open formats;
- Providing all relevant documentation and explanation for the data and/or datasets;
- Obtaining the consent of stakeholders involved in key actors and stakeholders' workshops and anonymizing and aggregating the data of interviews;
- In case of copyright on raw data derived, collected or elaborated from pre-existing databases or other sources (i.e. papers, book chapters, journal articles, reports, video and audio sources), collected data are made available if the reproduction and sharing are allowed by expressed permissions of the right holders or by applicable copyright exceptions and exemptions. Specifically, reproductions and communications of summaries of texts and other protected works are permitted for illustration purposes for scientific research, provided that the source, including the author's name, is acknowledged and provided that the use does not conflict with the exploitation of the source and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of right holders. Otherwise, only aggregate data resulting from the analysis are openly published. Anyway, when the sources are freely

available online in their original repositories, but direct reproduction is not allowed, a detailed account of how the dataset was created from the original datasets is available. Raw data consisting of full-texts are not made available without copyright holders' permission.

For these data that fall under some of the restrictions cited above and for which it is not possible to take any action to make them shareable, the EU allows complete closure or restricted access to them. The data cannot be made accessible openly on account of privacy issues and will be held in secure local systems with a password and regular backups at each involved partner institution. They will be preserved for at least five years beyond the project. The request of access to restricted data by single researchers, research institutions, reviewers and committees, aimed for example at verifying the quality of the research results, shall be addressed to the contact persons indicated in each dataset identified (this information will be included in an Annex). In general, within the limits of what has been indicated in the privacy policy, non-anonymized authorized data shall be provided on motivated request to single researchers, researcher institutions, reviewers and committees while non-anonymized not-authorized data shall be provided only to EC and publication reviewers. NOVASOIL final DMP will indicate the versions or parts of the datasets that cannot be freely shared providing the specific motivations.

Shareable data underlying the project publications will be deposited in institutional or public data repositories (see Tables 2 and 3) along with the metadata, relevant documentation and machine-readable licenses that allow re-use, at the time of the publisher's acceptance of the manuscripts.

The other research data produced within the project will be described and archived with all key documentation and machine-readable licenses allowing re-use in the chosen repositories for long-term preservation and future accessibility and re-use with different embargo periods (max 7 years) to permit all research groups to complete the analysis and publish the project results beyond the project.

After the embargo period, the research data will still be usable indefinitely since the repositories chosen for archiving guarantee long-term preservation.

Data underlying articles stemming from the project and published beyond the project will be deposited in the chosen repository at the latest at the time of the editorial acceptance of the manuscript to permit crosslinking between the publication and the data. Public access to these data will be given at the same time of publication.

Table 2. Summary of repositories identified by the consortium

Repository name	URL	Type	Partner
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org	Multi-disciplinary	EVENOR, UNIPI
ARPI UNIPI	https://arpi.unipi.it/	Institutional	UNIPI
NBU	https://eprints.nbu.bg/	Institutional	NBU

mediaTUM	https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013102	Institutional	TUM
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Table 3. Features of the pre-selected repositories

Repository name	Permanent ID	OpenAIRE compatibility?	Indexed in re3data catalogue?
ZENODO	DOI	OpenAIRE 3.0 (OA, funding), OpenAIRE data (funded, referenced datasets)	Yes, https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468
NBU		Yes	
mediaTUM	DOI	YES	https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013102

To facilitate intelligibility, access and re-use, the datasets will be deposited in only one data repositories along with all key documentation explaining data collection procedures and analysis. The final data repository will be discussed and selected in the updated version of DMP. In general, there is no need to use specific software to access project data, since researchers convert the data into open formats. In case of particular software is used in data processing, full explanation and instructions will be included in the deposited documentation (a summary of the tools and software which could be necessary to the re-use datasets are described in Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of tools and software for enabling re-use of the datasets

Tools/Software	Type of data
Open spreadsheet and document editors, such as OpenOffice or LibreOffice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numerical or textual tabular data - Qualitative textual data - Statistical data - Transcript from audio data
Free CSV file viewers, such as CSV viewer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numerical or textual tabular data - Simulation model data - Statistical data
R, free software environment for statistical computing and graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical data
(NBU) Python	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical data

3.3 Making data interoperable

To ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability, all datasets will be described by using standard descriptive. In addition, all relevant documentation explaining codebooks, users' manuals, data collection procedures and analysis will be available along with the data to guarantee intelligibility, reproducibility and validation of the project findings.

Variables names of data derived from official sources will be consistent with the source names. Variable names of data derived from surveys match the survey question items as closely as possible.

3.4 Increase data re-use (licensing)

NOVASOIL will distribute the shareable data by adopting licenses that allow there-use of the data and the datasets in their entirety by other scholars and stakeholders. The datasets will be available mainly under the Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0 and Open Data Commons ODC-BY.

CC BY 4.0 license permits users to freely share, modify, and use the data, subject only to full credit to the author(s). ODC-BY is a license specifically drafted for Open Data projects that work under the condition of compatibility with Open Data projects that works under the condition of compatibility with Open Access requirements, interoperability and re-use.

In general, data will be openly available as underlying data necessary to validate the research results immediately at the time of the publication of the corresponding scientific peer-reviewed papers. Some datasets will be underlying data of public deliverables, in these cases an embargo period (max 7 years) will applied to them in to allow full exploitation of research results by the Partners.

Data will be given a full citation from official project publications and web site and they will be made available in open formats through institutional public data repositories compliant with OpenAIRE requirements that guarantee long-term preservation of the archived items. Therefore, they will be re-usable by third parties also after the end of the project.

As the data collected or generated by the project are heterogenous, the quality of the data will be carefully assured using different approaches.

3.5 Allocation of resources

Usually, making data FAIR requires a certain amount of researchers' time and investments in infrastructures. In the NOVASOIL case, costs for long-term deposit and preservation of public shareable data will be null because the chosen repositories do not apply fees for archiving and data curation.

During the project, a cloud storage solution has been adopted to share data among partners. The cost of activating and maintaining it for the duration of the project are covered by the project budget. The budget covers also the costs related to the project website setting up.

Costs related to data management and documentation, conversion of proprietary data files into open formats and deposit procedures will be estimated at the end of the project.

Furthermore, the activities related to the DMP (including guidance on data management and open access issues, coordinating the Partners, and preparing the DMP) are estimated about 3 Person-Months for the whole duration of the project but, additional Person-Month may be required at the end of the project.

Responsible for data management are the creators of the datasets who are generally the team leaders directly involved in research data organization and collection (Table 5).

Researchers are encouraged to identify themselves with the unique persistent identifier ORCID. Registration is free of charge for researchers and allows for automated linkages between the researchers and allows for automated linkages between the researched identity and his research activities and outputs.

Table 5. Summary and contacts of the research team leaders responsible for the datasets

Team	Leader	ORCID ID (if available)	email
EVENOR	Anaya-Romero, María	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6819-0291	m.anaya@evenor-tech.com
ZSA	Inga Berzina	No ORCID	inga@zemniekusaeima.lv
NBU	Ekatherina Tzvetanova-Georgieva	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0788-8295	ecvetanova@nbu.bg
TUM	Fabian Frick	0000-0001-7017-9745	fabian.frick@tum.de
METK	Kalvi Tamm	0000-0001-6026-9528	kalvi.tamm@metk.agri.ee
UNIFI	Daniele Vergamini	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0721-826X	daniele.vergamini@unifi.it

As well as, Partners are encouraged to identify and credit all contributors (Table 6) participating in data management activities.

Table 6. Summary of the team members which contribute or are directly involved in the datasets creation and management

Team	Member	Role	ORCID ID (if available)
EVENOR	Anaya-Romero, María	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6819-0291
	González-Peñaloza, Felix	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5284-0760

	Blanco-Velázquez, Francisco José	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8031-5357
	Bravo-García, Javier	Project member	https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0001-6305-4346
	Alonso-Martín, Fernando	Project member	https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1082-0467
ZALF			
ZSA	Inga Berzina	Project Member	No ORCID
NBU	Ekatherina Tzvetanova	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0788-8295
	Dimitre Nikolov	WP 3 leader	
	Krasimir Kostenarov	Project member	
TUM	Fabian Frick	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7017-9745
TUM	Carina Obergröbner	Project member	
METK	Kalvi Tamm	Project member	0000-0001-6026-9528
	Tiina Talve	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8659-5759
	Merili Toom	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8779-1025
	Taavi Võsa	Project member	
	Tiina Köster	Project member	
UNIFI	Daniele Vergamini	Project member	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0721-826X

3.6 Data security

Data sharing among Partners does not contain sensitive data because they are anonymized.

At each institution, research data are stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives accessible through institutional passwords periodically modified according to national law provisions for data security and protected by regularly updated antiviruses. None of the project data is left inadvertently available.

All the research materials stored in computers are subject to regular backups to safeguard them from accidental losses. If mobile devices are used to store data files, they must be kept in a safe place accessible only to the researchers involved and/or encrypted with ad-hoc software.

A cloud storage solution has been adopted for data sharing among research teams. In this case, regular backups of the data will be performed to ensure data recovery. Finally, all partners are asked to keep locally updated copies of all their files.

3.7 Ethical aspects

Research in NOVASOIL involves questionnaires and surveys with adult participants, stakeholders' workshops, webinars, etc. All personal data collected within the NOVASOIL project from questionnaires, surveys, etc will be carefully protected in compliance with relevant national data protection legislation of the EU member states (EU 2016/679 GDPR) and associated partners.

As a general principle, personal data resulting from the project activity will be separated from the research results, and are handled by different members of the research teams. In regards to the respondents in the survey, they will be selected at random and their name and address are not recorded. The data will be stored in a way not to allow the identification of the subject, adopting measures for pseudonymisation; results of questionnaires or interviews will be transmitted or available to the other project partners as anonymous data.

Data collected that are potentially sensitive as well as personal characteristics that are strictly necessary for theoretical reasons and to the benefit of the research, could be collected.

Files containing questionnaire data for statistical analysis, transcripts of interviews, stakeholders' workshops, webinars and transcripts of field observations, photos, minutes, videos, action diaries, etc. are stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard drives of the research institutions accessible through institutional password modified periodically and protected by regularly updated antiviruses. Files containing "sensitive" data will be stored encrypted. Password-protected and encrypted files are accessible only to authorized members of the research teams receiving preliminarily specific information and training on the procedures for data collection, storage etc. None of the project data will be left inadvertently available by being left on desks or in unlocked rooms. All the research materials stored in computers are subjected to back up regularly (according to each institutions' regulations) to safeguard them from accidental losses.

Data and information collected from questionnaires are disseminated and published only in an aggregate and/or anonymous form. Publications report aggregate data and do not contain information that may permit the identification of individual participants unless they previously have accepted.

Data that are not shareable will be stored by the team responsible for their collection and management for the time required by the international scientific community (at least 5 years after the conclusion of the research project) and will be subsequently destroyed. When personal data are no longer necessary for the research, they are immediately destroyed. Qualitative

data files are publicly accessible as long as any information that can lead to the identification of an individual participant will be deleted.

4. Datasets overview

The following table (Table 7) offers an overview of the datasets expected from the project and is described more in detail in Annex. It will be updated according to the DMP changes and variations.

Additional information of the datasets expected:

1. Information from case studies: soil data collected from case studies will be shared in Zenodo. Same dataset will be shared with EUSO.
2. Consumer acceptance: surveys carried out and information collected will be shared following GDPR rules.
3. Producer adoption: surveys carried out and information collected will be shared following GDPR rules.
4. Inventory of incentives: List of inventories identified around case studies will be shared.
5. Mapping of incentives: full description of the main incentives related case studies and location will be detailed in a dataset that will be shared.
6. Community of Practice: anonymised list of key actors interested to be part of the NOVASOIL CoP will be shared following GDPR rules. Contact details of the National Contact Points (member responsible of the CoP from NOVASOIL' consortium)

Table 7. Datasets list

Table acronyms and abbreviations: # = data set progressive number ID, LB = WP lead beneficiary, PP = project phase (starting month-ending month), CT = creator team in charge of curating the data set, NYC = not yet collected, C = collected, NYG = not yet generated, G = generated, A = available, E = available after the embargo, AE = available at the end of the project.

#	W P	L B	TASK	PP	CT	DATASET Title	SOURC E	STATUS
1	1	1. 4	Coordination of Case Studies	1-36	EVENOR	NOVASOIL_WP1_Task1.4_Data collection from case studies_date	C, G	A (in Zenodo)
2	2	T U M	2.3 Assessment of Upscaling potential	14-35	TUM	T2.3_consumer_acceptance	NYC	(confidential data)
3	2	T U M	2.3 Assessment of Upscaling potential	14-35	TUM	T2.3_producer_adoption	NYC	(confidential data)
4	3	N B U	3.1 Mapping of existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models	1-8	NBU	T3.1_incentives_inventory_date	C	A (in the Tool-Box)
5	3	N B U	3.1 Mapping of existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models	1-8	NBU	T3.1_incentives_mapping_date	C	A (in the Tool-Box)
6	5	5. 3	Community of Practice approach implementation	1-36	EVENOR	NOVASOIL_WP5_Task5.3_Community of Practice_date	G	(confidential data)

6 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for NOVASOIL Datasets

The datasets generated within the NOVASOIL project will adhere to strict Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) guidelines to ensure the protection, accessibility, and appropriate reuse of the data. These datasets will encompass various types of information, including numerical, textual, and simulation model data. Below is a description of the IPR considerations for the expected datasets:

Ownership and Licensing

Ownership of the datasets will reside with the organizations that create them. Each dataset will be governed by specific licenses, ensuring that intellectual property is protected while allowing for data reuse under certain conditions. Most datasets will be licensed under Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) or Open Data Commons (ODC-BY), allowing others to freely share and adapt the data provided that appropriate credit is given to the creators. This ensures alignment with the project's FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles.

Copyright and Third-Party Data

In cases where data includes third-party content (e.g., from public or external datasets), permission from the original data owner will be obtained to ensure compliance with copyright laws. This includes adherence to confidentiality agreements, personal data protections (under GDPR), and proprietary limitations. If data cannot be shared due to third-party restrictions, they will be stored securely and made available under controlled access.

In the data compilation from case studies, permission from the original data owner would be required.

Access and Data Sharing

While NOVASOIL strives to make its datasets openly available, there will be cases where data access is restricted to protect sensitive information, such as personal data or proprietary content. For these restricted datasets, access will be managed by designated project members and may be available upon request for specific research purposes. These datasets will remain in secure repositories for a minimum of five years post-project, ensuring that interested parties can verify or build upon the project's results. Final repository will be chosen for the next DMP.

Data Citation and Acknowledgment

Each dataset will be assigned a persistent identifier (such as a DOI) to ensure proper attribution and citation. Users of the datasets are required to acknowledge the original creators in any derivative works or publications. This approach supports both legal and ethical compliance while promoting the reuse of NOVASOIL datasets within the scientific and business communities.

Long-Term Preservation

All datasets, including their related metadata and documentation, will be stored in long-term, open-access repositories, ensuring that they are accessible for future use. The datasets will be deposited in one institutional or public repositories such as Zenodo, mediaTUM, or other project-partner repositories that guarantee data preservation and compliance with OpenAIRE standards.

By adhering to these IPR guidelines, NOVASOIL ensures that its datasets can be reused while protecting the intellectual property of project partners and contributing to global knowledge on soil health and sustainable business models.

7 Acknowledgments

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Annex 1: List of expected datasets

This annex will be updated in forthcoming DMP versions.

Template:

WPX – title

Lead: YY

Participants: YY, YZ, etc

WPX Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum

#	Current status	Dataset' title
ID	(Repository, Identification Type)	-
Version		1
Team in charge		YY
Creator/s		
Contributors		(INCLUDE HERE ALL PARTNERS INVOLVED)
Contact person/s		
Contents		

WP2 – Analysis and Development of Business Models to Promote Soil Health

Lead: TUM

Participants: All

WP2 identifies most promising soil management strategies to promote soil health, reviews existing business models related to soil health, investigates acceptance of business models on both the land managers' and consumer side. In a last task, its objective is to co-develop improved business models together with stakeholders.

2	NYC	T2.3_consumer_acceptance
ID	(Repository, Identification Type)	(confidential data)
Version		1
Team in charge		TUM
Creator/s		Carina Obergröbner, Fabian Frick

Contributors	tbd
Contact person/s	Fabian Frick
Contents	Data from a choice experiment on consumer acceptance of selected soil health business models.

2	NYC	T2.3_producer_acceptance
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		(confidential data)
Version		1
Team in charge		TUM
Creator/s		Carina Obergröbner, Fabian Frick
Contributors		tbd
Contact person/s		Fabian Frick
Contents		Data from a choice experiment on producer acceptance of selected soil health business models.

WP1 –Case Study Dataset

Lead: EVENOR

Participants: EVENOR

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Tamarguillo_Park
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17422778
Version		1
Team in charge		EVENOR
Creator/s		Blanco-Velázquez FJ, Alonso Martín F, Bravo-García J, González-Peñaloza F and Anaya-Romero M
Contributors		EVENOR
Contact person/s		Francisco José Blanco-Velázquez
Contents		This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: TUM

Participants: TUM

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_CO2_Land_Initiative
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ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17423016
Version	1
Team in charge	TUM
Creator/s	Frick Fabian, Obergröbner Carina
Contributors	TUM
Contact person/s	Fabian Frick
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: ZSA

Participants: ZSA

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_DIH_System
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17423074
Version		1
Team in charge		ZSA
Creator/s		Inga Berzina, Valters Zelcs
Contributors		ZSA
Contact person/s		Inga Berzina
Contents		This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: NBU

Participants: NBU

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Organic_Vineyards
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17423850

Version	1
Team in charge	NBU
Creator/s	Nikolov Dimitre, Banov Martin, Tzvetanova Ekatherina
Contributors	NBU
Contact person/s	Dimitre Nikolov
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: ZSA

Participants: ZSA

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_DIH_System
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://zenodo.org/records/17415794
Version		1
Team in charge		ZSA
Creator/s		Berzina Inga, Zelcs Valters
Contributors		ZSA
Contact person/s		Inga Berzina
Contents		This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: ASAJA

Participants: ASAJA, EVENOR

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Olive_Integrated_Production
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ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17423882
Version	1
Team in charge	ASAJA
Creator/s	Jose Fernando Robles
Contributors	ASAJA, EVENOR
Contact person/s	Javier Bravo García
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: UNIFI

Participants: UNIFI

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Ciraa_Cover_Cropping
ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424355	
Version	1	
Team in charge	UNIFI	
Creator/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi	
Contributors	UNIFI	
Contact person/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi	
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.	

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Ciraa_MASCOT
ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424199	
Version	1	

Team in charge	UNIPI
Creator/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi
Contributors	UNIPI
Contact person/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.
1	Generated (not yet available)
ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424319
Version	1
Team in charge	UNIPI
Creator/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi
Contributors	UNIPI
Contact person/s	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi
Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: METK

Participants: METK

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)
ID (Repository, Identification Type)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424047
Version	1
Team in charge	METK
Creator/s	Kalvi Tamm
Contributors	METK
Contact person/s	Kalvi Tamm

Contents	This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.
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WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: UPM

Participants: UPM

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Organic_Vineyards_UPM
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424104
Version		1
Team in charge		UPM
Creator/s		Ana Iglesias, Alvaro Francisco Sordo Ward
Contributors		UPM
Contact person/s		Alvaro Francisco Sordo Ward
Contents		This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.

WP1 – Case Study Dataset

Lead: UNIFE

Participants: UNIFE

The dataset uploaded in Zenodo contains soil data from the case study.

1	Generated (not yet available)	NOVASOIL_WP1_Dataset_Organic_District_Of_Sands
ID (Repository, Identification Type)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17431204
Version		1
Team in charge		UNIFE
Creator/s		EVENOR
Contributors		UNIFE
Contact person/s		

Contents

This dataset contains data on the monitoring variables selected from the case studies. The information has been organised under different categories for their easy re-use and according to the objectives of the case study and their business model.